

TRANSLATION PRINCIPLES OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS RELATED TO INSURANCE TERMINOLOGY

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Annotation: The problems of phraseological units related to insurance terminology, their translation principles, peculiarities are discussed in the article. Therefore, accurate, high-quality and perfect translation determines the level of stability of cooperation, and this process provides an opportunity to demonstrate professionalism. In addition to them comparative analyses of phraseological units related to insurance terminology are given in Uzbek and English.

Key words: phraseological units, translation principles, insurance, terminology, comparative analyses.

At a time when modern technology offers its capabilities, the quality of translation of texts in the field of insurance, of course, plays an important role in the process of negotiating financial transactions with foreign partners. Therefore, accurate, high-quality and perfect translation determines the level of stability of cooperation. In such cases, the translator, in particular, requires specialists in the field of insurance to have knowledge and skills not only in the field but also in related areas of finance and economics, to understand the nuances of insurance terms, to be aware of their specificity in industry documents, oral and written translation. .

A distinctive feature of English economics, finance, and insurance texts is that their textual language is usually expressive in terms of emotional coloring. Based on the analysis, such texts occupy an intermediate position between scientific prose and journalism in terms of methodology. Various methodological techniques found in articles describing the nature of economics, finance, and insurance: figurative

expressions, proverbs, metaphors, metonymy, stylistic devices such as word play, are used in these texts.

Although the Uzbek language has less emotion in the works of the mentioned field and its language is closer to the language of scientific prose, the figurativeness and general methodological color of the original should be preserved as much as possible in the translation process. In this section we will consider some issues of sufficiently conveying the stylistic features of the original.

Scientific research in the field of phraseology began at the beginning of the last century by such scientists as M.V.Lomonosov, A.A.Potebnya, Sh.Balli. Scholars have independently drawn an in-depth analysis of the etymology of these units as an object of lexicography.

By the 1930s, E.D. Polivanov, V.V. Vinogradov and a number of scientists in the former Soviet Union had put forward new theories, methods and issues related to the translation of the field.

From the late 1960s onwards, representatives of German linguistics began to manifest themselves in the development of the field of phraseology (East), but it was also occasionally referred to in English linguistics. Early English theoretical views on the field of phraseology were studied by Weinreich (Weinreich, 1969) as part of a transformational grammar approach by scholars such as Arnold (Arnold, 1973) and Lipka (Lipka, 1974).

In the process of translation, it is wrong to understand phraseology in the sense of "broad" and "narrow", it must be understood in one sense. Regardless of how they are classified as linguistic units, aphorisms, proverbs or sayings, fixed speech formulas, "winged words", if they meet the definition of phraseology, they can meet the requirements, that is, they are structurally equivalent to a phrase or sentence. any fixed lexical semantic units mentioned in dictionaries, which have a figurative, generalized meaning, the lexical elements of which are partially or completely portable, must be included in the scope of phraseological units.

The translation of figurative phraseological units in English into Uzbek can theoretically be divided into four groups:

1) units with complete alternatives in Uzbek, e.g.: *Hands are tied* - *оёқ қўли боғланган* (phrase in the Uzbek language). In this classification, phraseological units are also present in the Uzbek language, and their meaning is the same as the original unit meaning.

In English: *I wish I could help you cut through all this red tape (another business idiom meaning administrative procedures) but my hands are tied. My boss won't let me (europelanguagejobs.com) – translation.:* *Мен сизга бу қоғозбозликни (бошқа бир бизнес ибораси маъмурий тартиб-қоидаларни англатади) кесиб ташлашга ёрдам беришни хоҳлардим, лекин менинг қўлларим боғланган. Раҳбарим рухсат бермайди.*

In a nutshell - *қисқаси, бир сўз билан айтганда* (phrase in the Uzbek language).

In English: *His weeks insurance meeting was, in a nutshell, extremely productive and informative (europelanguagejobs.com) – translation.:* *унинг ушбу ҳафтадаги суғурта учрашуви, бир сўз билан айтганда, жуда самарали ва маълумотга бой бўлди.*

Save for a rainy day – *оғир кунга сақламоқ* (phrase in the Uzbek language).

Инглиз тилида: *Every company, just like every individual, tries to save for a rainy day (economist.com)– translation.:* *Ҳар бир компания, худди ҳар бир шахс каби, оғир кун учун маблағ тежашига ҳаракат қилади.*

There are not many phraseological units in the field of insurance, which have an alternative in English to Uzbek, but they are sufficient for proof, and they include the following compounds. Including: *live from hand to mouth* - *қўл учида кун кўриш* (кунлик ҳаражат учун пул топиб хаёт кечириш); *cover one's back* – *кимнидир кетини ёпиш* (бировни қарзини тўлаш) кабилар киради.

Apparently, in the field of insurance, alternative terms are almost not a problem in translation, but the translator is required to know the alternatives, especially in simultaneous translation, its importance is very valuable. Our analysis

has shown that it is advisable to use similar alternatives when translating from Uzbek to English.

2) Phraseological units that are partially compatible in the process of translating from English to Uzbek. ***By the book*** - ***китобдагидек, кўнгилдагидек*** (phrase in the Uzbek language). meaning: *To do things strictly by the rules* - *ишни қатъий қоидага мувофиқ бажариш*. In this classification, phraseological units are also present in the Uzbek language, and their meaning is close to the meaning of the original unit.

In English: *I don't want to take any chances of getting caught by the financial regulators and having to pay significant fines. We have to do everything **by the book*** (europelanguagejobs.com) – **translation.:** *Мен молиявий тартибга соливчилар томонидан ушланиб қолиш ва катта миқдордаги жарималарни тўлаш имкониятига эга бўлишни хоҳламайман. Биз ҳамма нарсани **китобдагидек** қилишимиз керак.*

Up in the air - (ҳавода) ***осилиб ётибди*** (ўзбек тили оғзаки нутқида учрайдиган ибора). In both languages, it is used for cases where the result of a process is abstract.

In English: *We were hoping to sign the contract by the end of the month, but there are still too many things **up in the air** we need to deal with first* (europelanguagejobs.com) – **translation.:** *Биз ой охиригача шартнома имзолашни умид қилган эдик, аммо биз биринчи навбатда шуғулланишимиз керак бўлган жуда кўп нарсалар ҳануз (ҳавода) **осилиб ётибди**.*

Phrases belonging to this group include the following. In particular, such phraseological units as *air cover* – *ҳаво сугуртаси* (авия ҳалокат қопламаси); *act of God* ((*сугурта соҳасида*) *қонуний равишда инсон назоратидан ташиқарида деб қабул қилинган ҳаракат*) -*худонинг иши*.

The industry units that make up this group are a process that causes relatively more translation problems. Therefore, it requires a very subtle approach from the

translator, i.e. to be able to find a descriptive expression of the whole lexical or phraseological unit that makes sense.

3) Phraseological compounds, proverbs or sayings, literary references (aphorisms) based on the life of the English people in English are included in this group, but in Uzbek there must be approximate equivalents. There are hundreds of linguistic-methodological means in the original source that express its national aspect, and it is very rare for such specific units to choose the same alternative means from the language of peoples with a different historical and cultural process. For example, *to carry coals to Newcastle* – direct translation of this phraseological unit translated as - *Нюкаслга кўмир олиб бормоқ*. Newcastle is the city with the most coal deposits in Britain. So it makes sense to *take a particular product to a place where there is a lot of that product*. In this example, the idea is expressed through a logical figurative expression. It corresponds to the Uzbek phrase *ўрмонга ўтин кўтариб бормоқ* (маъноси - эҳтиёж бўлмаган жойга бирор нарса етказиб бериш). Therefore, it is more effective for the translator to use the phrase to carry firewood to the forest instead of the literal translation to carry coals to Newcastle to reconcile the meaning between the original and the language of translation. In some cases, even if there is an Uzbek alternative, from a stylistic point of view, it is better to use descriptive translation techniques to explain the meaning of the sentence. Therefore, it is also useful to translate the phrase to carry coals to Newcastle as doing something unnecessary (redundant).

Research on the comparative, translational, structural-typological aspects of phraseological units opens a wide way to solve the general problems of phraseology. In general, the field of translation is the reason why the phraseological units of any field develop, develop, form in the second language without losing the value of the original language. In recent years, significant research work has been carried out by Turkic scholars and translators, and a number of achievements have been made in the field. In addition, the study of national and cultural specifics of phraseological units of languages of different systems through the field of translation studies, the

analysis of systemic and semantic types of phraseological units, ethnospecific features of world linguistics.

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